

Optimizing global vegetation model with model-data integration approach

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Abstract

We present a model-data integration framework for optimizing global vegetation model in this report. Dynamic global vegetation models (DGVMs) are important tools to understand the trajectories of the terrestrial ecosystems and carbon cycle in response to the future climate change. However, the simulations of dynamical processes of vegetation can well be biased by the empirical or even arbitrary parameterization in the model. Our goal is to build a generic framework of gauging the parameters in the model with observational data to achieve a better representation of vegetation and its response to climate. We here show a case study in which the global dynamic vegetation model LPJmL (Lund-Potsdam-Jena managed Land) is optimized with observational site-level carbon flux and phenological datasets. We show a substantial reduction of bias and variabilities in the simulation of vegetation phenology and productivity after the parameters are optimized with the data-model integration approach. This is a proof of concept that this approach can be theoretically applied to improve the performance of other DGVMs.

¹ Based on the CRediT Contributor Roles Taxonomy: <https://credit.niso.org/>

I. Introduction

The response of terrestrial ecosystems to climate change is one of the most uncertain processes in the global carbon cycle. The uncertainties are caused by the complicated interaction between vegetation and climate which results in a large spread in the simulations of vegetation distribution, allocation, productivity, carbon turnover, etc., by different DGVMs. However, the availability of global Earth Observations that mostly derived from satellite images can potentially assist to constrain DGVMs within a model-data integration (MDI) framework. By incorporating the observations into modeling framework, the biases and uncertainties of the parameters that determine biogeochemical processes can be reduced. However, the challenge of this MDI approach is to harmonize all available earth observations and optimize at the same time. We solve this by establishing algorithms that can give a structured database which is shown the below sections.

II. Results

The flowchart of the implemented model-data integration framework is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. A schematic flowchart that shows the MDI framework.

a) Implemented Solution

We implemented the MDI framework as a package for the R language (Figure 1). As shown in the Figure 1, the observational data is used to reduce the distance between model output and observations by changing relevant parameters iteratively until a certain criteria is met. The package contains functions and classes to store parameter and configuration files for the DGVM model runs, to read and pre-process the datasets used for MDI and to perform the

optimization (Figure 2). The optimization algorithm is a genetic optimization algorithm (GENOUD) used to estimate model parameters.

Figure 2. Overview of functional dependencies in the package.

As a case study, we optimized LPJmL parameterization by using various site-level carbon fluxes including GPP (gross primary production), Reco (ecosystem respiration) and NEE (net ecosystem exchange) as well as remote-sensed ecological variable FAPAR (fraction of absorbed photosynthetically active radiation). Our results (Figure 3) show a large reduction in the overall cost function, indicating a suite of improved global and biome-specific parameters in the model that lead to more realistic simulation of carbon fluxes. Specifically, GPP and Reco have a large reduction of 90% and 92% in the cost function, respectively, indicating the parameters that governs the processes of carbon uptake such as photosynthesis and respiratory processes are substantially biased. By optimizing those parameters with site-level data, we were able to improve the performance of the model therefore results in a better simulation of ecological processes.

Figure 3. Changes in the cost function between simulated and observed carbon fluxes by using the MDI approach.

b) Data and Software availability

One can access the repository of the R package from here https://github.com/fanfan987/NFDI_MDI.git. The license (AGPL-3.0 license) is included in the repository. Documentation and relevant resources are provided in the repository.

c) Innovation and FAIRness

The Innovation of this tool is that global vegetation models can be optimized with observational datasets in a unified framework. We provide full open access to the public in which repository the MDI framework is well described.

III. Challenges and Gaps

Due to the time limitation of the pilot project and due to the preliminary developments within NFDI4Earth, we could not make the MDI more generic. However, our results show high potential of this tool which can be used for other models and studies. We wish to link the functionality of the MDI framework to a data repository or data cube that stores several Earth observation datasets in order to reduce data pre-processing efforts. Ideally, this should be done through an API.

IV. Relevance for the community and NFDI4Earth

The researchers or communities that focus on simulating changes in vegetation in response of climate can considering using similar approach to gauge the parameters in their model. One can adapt the MDI framework to their own use since the code and algorithm can be accessed publicly. Atmospheric science, earth system science, ecological studies can benefit from this tool. The MDI framework is especially designed for researchers in Earth Sciences who is interested in modeling biogeochemical processes that are complicated and therefore difficult to grasp. The framework can be potentially adapted to one's own modeling framework although the prototype we show in this report is for LPJmL per se. The adaption of the MDI framework to a specific model requires regional or global earth observations that can be used in comparison with model output. The adaption also requires a deep understanding of the data I/O process as shown Figure 2. We will be willing to give suggestions and advice to researchers that are interested in adapting our tool to their use.

V. Future Directions

For the researchers who are interested in implementing the MDI framework their own studies. We suggest they first understand the core idea of this package and revise the data input portal so that a specific model can be implemented. One main issue is that the model is designed for LPJmL. Therefore, the protocols and interface of the MDI tool need to be revised to fulfill the requirement of a specific study. The main reason that the

planned goals cannot be achieved is the time frame (one year) of the project is not enough for accomplishing such a generic modeling framework that needs large amount of time. Therefore, future interested users of the MDI framework for their own model should be anticipate heavy and long-term involvement in revising and testing the model. However, the advantage of using the MDI framework is evident as shown in previous work that the parameterization can be largely optimized.